

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL RELATIONS BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN AND THE REPUBLIC OF LATVIA IN THE MODERN ERA

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Abstract

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the former republics began developing direct political relationships to strengthen their cooperation. Modern Azerbaijan places significant importance on collaboration with Latvia in regional organizations, particularly within the framework of the Council of the Baltic Sea States. This collaboration plays a crucial role in intensifying integration processes in the Baltic-Black Sea-Caspian region. Latvia recognizes Azerbaijan as the main country in the Black Sea-Caspian region that provides Europe with energy resources. Additionally, Latvia has always opposed separatism and supports the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan. The main purpose of this article is to analyze the development of political cooperation between two countries using diplomatic documents, media materials, and government documentation. The method used for this study was the descriptive-comparative method.

Keywords: Latvia, Azerbaijan, Political Cooperation, European Union, Regional Cooperation.

Introduction. Several reasons make political cooperation between the republics of the former Soviet Union important. After the fall of the USSR, there were significant political changes in its former territories. The Baltic nations joined the European Union, while the South Caucasian countries of Armenia and Azerbaijan became part of the CIS. Some republics, such as Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia, are also aiming to move closer to the European space. These processes directly impact global security issues and Russia's political interests as the most powerful state in the region. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze the main political cooperation directions between EU and CIS member countries to identify main challenges to global stability. Global security is directly linked to political and cultural ties between EU and CIS member countries. EU and CIS member countries' political rapprochement necessitates the study of methods, ways, and scope of their political cooperation.

Political cooperation issues between member-states of EU and CIS, and specifically between Latvia and Azerbaijan, are analyzed by domestic and foreign scholars [3; 10; 11; 1; 8]. Azerbaijani scholars generally pay special attention to political and economic cooperation between EU member countries and Azerbaijan and determine the main priorities of the republic's foreign policy [13; 14]. Western scholars contrarily, study issues of democracy, energy and global security, political transformation, and the EU's role in resolving conflicts in the South Caucasus [4; 5; 7; 12]. Based on governmental and diplomatic documents, as well as media outlets, this article aims to study the main directions of political cooperation between Azerbaijan and Latvia. The descriptive-comparative method is applied for this study.

Foreign policy of the European Union in the South Caucasus went through several stages of development. The changes coincided with a rethinking of the EU's global role within the union itself. For the South Caucasus countries, it was a period of strengthening their national identity and defining of political priorities. Despite belonging to a single region and initially similar conditions, each country of the EU adheres to its own cooperation paradigm. In this situation, partnerships with various players serve as an incentive to discuss the foundations of statehood of the countries, review established ties and formulate their own strategy for joining the international community. The EU's relationship with Azerbaijan is based on the country's non-entry into any political blocs and the fulfillment of those EU requirements that meet state interests. The Azerbaijani government is critical of the EU's foreign policy, largely due to its stance on the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. That's why Azerbaijan places great importance on cooperating with individual EU member countries and building especially warm relations with the former republics of the Soviet Union, which are now members of the EU. One of these areas of cooperation is political collaboration between Azerbaijan and Latvia.

Political cooperation between Azerbaijan and Latvia.

The Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Latvia began direct political cooperation after declaring independence in the early 1990s. On July 8, 1997, a significant meeting took place between the President of Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, and the President of Latvia, Guntis Ulmanis at the NATO summit in Madrid. The meeting aimed to discuss the possibilities of strengthening the relationship between both countries and the leaders talked about the prospects of future development for their nations. An International Conference on

the topic of "Baltic-Black Sea cooperation: towards an integrated Europe without dividing lines" was held in Yalta on September 10, 1999. During the conference, a meeting was conducted between the presidents of the two countries. Meetings among the top political leaders of the countries in the late 1990s helped to define the contours of further political cooperation and set priorities for each side.

As part of its foreign policy course, Azerbaijan is attempting to navigate between key regional powers, including Russia, the USA, Turkey, and Iran. One of Azerbaijan's primary foreign policy goals was to restore its territorial integrity, followed by integration into European and Euro-Atlantic structures, and then cooperation with international and regional organizations [2]. As part of its foreign policy, Azerbaijan is pursuing a multi-vector approach to balance relations with different regional and global players. Balance and pragmatism are the cornerstones of the country's foreign policy [6, p.66]. Today's foreign policy aims to strengthen interactions with Western countries. This includes not only a focus on interacting with NATO and the EU, but also maintaining regular communication on all political, economic, and military fronts. There are also ongoing EU-Azerbaijan Cooperation Councils in place to facilitate this interaction. The Republic of Azerbaijan sees partnership with Euro-Atlantic structures to support overall security, economic development, and democracy.

Latvia's participation in the North Atlantic Alliance has been established as the basis of national foreign policy by its leadership and is considered a central element of the collective security system both now and in the long term [17, p.117-118]. Latvian leadership considers participation in the European Union as a reliable and stable development opportunity for the republics. Latvia's foreign policy in the South Caucasus is largely determined by the main directions of the EU Eastern Partnership program. Through the Eastern Partnership program, Latvia aims to strengthen its own presence in the Euro-Atlantic region while supporting the consolidation of Western influence in Russia's neighboring countries [5, p. 72]. As part of this program, the Latvian government has pledged to aid Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine, by encouraging their cooperation with the European Union. Additionally, Latvia aims to actively involve Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Belarus in the program. Latvia is actively developing relations with Azerbaijan, considering it a key player in the EU's energy supply diversification strategy, and encourages the Euro-Atlantic ambitions of Baku [18, p. 53]. Riga has always confirmed its commitment to the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan.

The accession of Latvia, Lithuania and Estonia to the EU has led to growing interest among European politicians to the post-Soviet space. The acquisition of independence by the former Soviet republics indicated the need building new relationships with the political leadership of these states. The European Union's interest in the South Caucasus countries is primarily aimed at ensuring stability on the Union's borders. Additionally, the EU serves as a role model for newly formed

states. The EU's interest in the South Caucasus countries is also driven by specific pragmatic interests, specifically in the supply of energy resources from the region.

The Eastern Partnership is the main ideological foundation for bilateral and multilateral relations in the CIS space. It demonstrates the strong influence of pragmatic national interests on the degree and depth of interaction between the EU and the participating countries [12, p. 360]. Political cooperation between Azerbaijan and Latvia mainly takes place within the framework of the Eastern Partnership program. This covers various aspects including the relations between the political leadership of the countries, cooperation of the parliaments, and diplomatic services. The political foundation for the relationship between the two countries is the Neighborhood Policy and the EU Global Strategy for foreign, and security policy. According to the EU's foreign policy in the early 2000s, neighboring countries were not given the opportunity to join the European Union soon. However, the situation crucially changed after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022.

Azerbaijan places great importance on political ties with EU member states to strengthen multi-level cooperation. Since 2004, representatives of political establishment of Azerbaijan and Latvia have regularly exchanged visits. Important issues that are discussed during these meetings are related to problems of national and regional security. The Ukrainian crisis of 2014 seriously affected Azerbaijan's foreign policy, increasing the state's fears about its own national sovereignty and the prospects for resolving the ethno-political conflict. The Ukrainian crisis revealed Azerbaijan's fundamental disagreement with the Russian foreign policy agenda and brought Azerbaijan even closer to the EU countries [19, p. 11].

In 2015, the EU Neighborhood Policy was revised along with the adoption of the new EU Global Strategy titled "Shared Vision, Common Approach: Strong Europe". This strategy was presented at the European Summit council on June 28, 2016. These events marked an important stage in the development of the EU's foreign policy towards neighboring countries. The EU Neighborhood Policy review process was based on the views of officials, the opinions of the expert community, civil society organizations, and individual EU citizens. The public consultation lasted four months, and a total of about 250 applications were received regarding EU neighborhood policies [15]. The new concept of EU foreign policy notes that political stabilization is ensured by the development of economic well-being and democratic institutions, which should contribute to the peaceful resolution of all conflicts.

The new global strategy of the EU contributed to the intensification of inter-parliamentary relations between Azerbaijan and Latvia. The cooperation's conceptual basis impacts the socio-economic and political development model, aligning it with European standards. Joining integration groups for countries such as Azerbaijan is an opportunity to use external resources for modernizing political and economic institutions. However, the summit that took place as part of the Eastern Partnership program in Vilnius in 2013 highlighted

the failure of the idea of a straightforward path of cooperation between the European Union and each of the South Caucasus countries. While Georgia initiated the Association Agreement, Azerbaijan refused to sign it. Azerbaijan stated that they wanted to prepare a document that would align with the level of their relations and cooperation with the European Union. Azerbaijan also confirmed that bilateral relations with EU member states are much more important. Under this approach, Azerbaijan and Latvia have signed several dozen documents. In 2017, they signed four agreements on the legal framework. The 2020 resolution of the Euro Nest Parliamentary Assembly mentions the "Trio 2030 Strategy" as a geopolitical instrument of the EU. It introduces differentiation between partner countries based on the characteristics of their political regimes.

As mentioned above, the failures of the Vilnius summit greatly spoiled the relationship between Azerbaijan and the EU. From 2012 to 2016 meetings of the Parliamentary Cooperation Committee were suspended. The committee was the only bilateral format of dialogue at the government and parliamentary levels. The mistrust of the Azerbaijani side was accompanied by negative statements assessment of European partners regarding the measures taken in country of reforms and the general political situation. In 2016, the Venice Commission of the Council of Europe criticized constitutional reform in Azerbaijan [9]. During this tense period, interparliamentary contacts between representatives of Azerbaijani and Latvian parliamentarians acquired particular importance.

Today the Azerbaijani-Latvian inter-parliamentary working group in the Parliament of Azerbaijan addresses political and social issues to strengthen cooperation between the two countries. The Latvian Saeim's group headed by Romans Naudiņš promotes cooperation with legislative representatives of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Constant meetings and political dialogues with Latvian parliamentarians will allow the adaptation of Azerbaijani law to European standards and will also help create separate institutions for legislative regulation specific areas and maintaining dialogue on this matter with the EU.

The diplomatic relations between the two countries are paving the way for their alignment with the EU's political model. This model encompasses a wide range of modernization efforts aimed at enhancing transparency in the regulation of state institutions, promoting the independence of the judiciary, maintaining stability of the electoral system, and supporting small and medium-sized enterprises. One of the steps to increasing the efficiency of diplomatic channels is the creation of a civil society platform consisting of Azerbaijani and European NGOs. It should be noted that the small Azerbaijani diaspora in Latvia plays an important role in this process.

The Azerbaijanis of Latvia are united in several societies, including 'Azeri' and 'Ojag' [16, p.12]. These societies, along with the diplomatic corps, help bring the Latvian and Azerbaijani peoples closer together politically and culturally. After signing an agreement between Azerbaijan and the EU in 2018, the areas of good governance, human rights, and the rule of law

were prioritized for cooperation from 2018-2020. This agreement also emphasized the importance of dialogue with civil society, combatting corruption, and the role of public organizations in regulating political processes. As a result, there has been an increase in efforts to address these issues. The attractiveness of cooperation between civil societies of Azerbaijan and Latvia through diaspora organizations lies in promoting the values of democracy and human rights and fundamental freedoms, which serves as the basis for political association and economic integration throughout the region.

Conclusion. The main lines and vectors of political cooperation between Latvia and Azerbaijan are determined by the Security Strategy of the EU and the South Caucasus. The EU highly appreciates the historical ties between the republics of the former Union and is building interaction with all regional actors. The European Union has agreements with the countries of the South Caucasus where regional stability and resolution of global issues are an important part of the agenda. The Comprehensive and Enhanced Partnership Agreement signed between Azerbaijan and Latvia states that both parties will make efforts to enhance conditions for regional cooperation, support open borders and cross-border partnerships, and promote good neighborly relations, and democratic development. These efforts are aimed at ensuring stability and security in both countries. EU's understanding of security is linked to inviolability principles of international law, the priority of diplomatic methods for resolving disagreements between countries, including the principle of territorial integrity and sovereignty of states. These principles fully coincide with the foreign policy course of the Republic of Azerbaijan and are the basis for cooperation with the Republic of Latvia in the field of politics.

For a long time, Azerbaijan successfully used the Latvian political platform to bring to the attention of European parliamentarians the realities of the Nagorno-Karabakh problem. The resolution of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and the restoration of Azerbaijan's territorial integrity would facilitate the development of a more progressive relationship between Latvia and Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan has always declared its support for the values of freedom, the rule of law and democracy as incentives for modernization countries. Azerbaijan considers its role important in bringing the European space closer to the Muslim world. President Ilham Aliyev called this an honorable mission of Azerbaijan. To implement this mission, Azerbaijan is leveraging its strong connections with the Baltic states.

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